

THE MARKETING EFFICIENCY, MARKETING COST, MARKETING MARGIN AND PRICE SPREAD OF MAKHANA AND THE CONSTRAINTS, SUGGESTIONS FOR MAKHANA GROWER IN THE STUDY AREA.

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(MS Received: 05.02.2023; MS Revised:06.03.2023; MS Accepted:07.03.2023)

MS 3027

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS,)

Abstract

Makhana or gorgon nut (*Euryale ferox*) is an aquatic crop belongs to Nymphaeaceae family and is grown in some district of North Bihar. The present study was under taken to study overview of marketing cost, marketing margin and price spread, constraints faced by farmers in Darbhanga district of Bihar. Combination of purposive stratified and random sampling technique were used for market functionaries and farmer selection were required for the purpose of the study. The data for the present study pertained to agriculture year 2021-2022. Secondary data was collected from secondary source like Market intermediate, market committee office, Research centre for makhana etc. The results revealed that on an average the marketing cost of the four different channel i.e, channel I, II, III, IV are Rs. 180.5, Rs. 335.5, Rs 786.5, and Rs. 1259. The average market margin of four different channel are Rs 50, Rs 240, Rs 680 and marketing efficiency of different channels are 20.39%, 11.99%, 5.53% & 4.95%. Cultivation of makhana has immense potential for enhancing the economic status of mallah community who are particularly engaged in its cultivation. Makhana cultivation is promoted to state government along with NRC, Darbhanga and training cum demonstration programme on cultivation practices should be imparted for efficient cultivation. Cultivation of makhana is fully organic and it should be promoted in developed countries of the world to increase export.

Keywords: - Makhana, *Euryale ferox*, Marketing efficiency, marketing margin, Constraints, Price spread.

Introduction

Makhana or gorgon nut (*Euryale ferox*) is an aquatic crop belongs to Nymphaeaceae family is boon to the rural poor people especially of north Bihar, Bengal & Lower Assam who have art of cultivating of makhana. The seed of makhana are popped and eaten as roasted as well as used in preparation of various kind of sweets and recipes. It has nutritional and medicinal properties and there is great potential of export of this crop in international market. The origin of makhana is considered to be in south east Asia and China from where it spread to all over part of the world. It is cultivated in tropical and sub-tropical region. In India it is cultivated in the state like Bihar, West Bengal, Manipur, Tripura, Assam, Jammu & Kashmir, Odisha, U.P Rajasthan and Madhya Pradesh. However commercially production of makhana is cultivated in North Bihar, Manipur, and west Bengal.

Materials and Methods

Selection of District

There are 38 district in Bihar out of which Darbhanga is selected purposively. It has been selected in view of the makhana cultivation in the economy of Bihar. Darbhanga has got the GI tag for makhana.

Selection of blocks:-

Out of 19 blocks under Darbhanga district, Kamtoul block has been selected based on the criteria of highest production in that area.

Selection of village:-

Selection of village is the third step of sampling. A complete list of village of selected block was 507. there 2.5 % of villages were selected randomly.

Analytical tool:-

Taking into consideration and convenience and survey method will be used for the collection of data selected farmer will be personally interviewed necessary information will be collected. Tabular method and some analytical tool will be adopted for the analysis of data.

Cost of marketing: -

The total cost incurred on marketing by various intermediaries involved in the sales and purchase of the product till it reaches the ultimate consumer will be computed as follows:

Garret Ranking

Garret ranking technique was used in order to rank the problem faced by the farmer's.

Result and discussion

To analyse Marketing cost, Marketing margin, and price spread of makhana in different channel.

Among this 80% of the makhana production is constitute by Bihar. In Bihar district like Darbhanga, Madhubani, Sitamarhi, Saharsa, Supaul, Araria, Kishanganj, Purnia, Katihar are the major grower of Makhana and they sell for commercially purpose also. The production of makhana seed is about 12000 MT which after processing convert into 40000 MT whose estimated value at the farmers end is about 250 crore. As the production of makhana till it reaches to the consumer it follow different channels of market according to the distant of consumer. The marketing cost of the different channel are i.e, channel I, II, III, IV are Rs. 180.5, Rs. 335.5, Rs 786.5, and Rs. 1259. The average market margin of four different channel are 50, Rs 240, Rs 680 and marketing efficiency of different channels are 20.39%, 11.99%, 5.53% & 4.95%.

$$C = C_f + C_{m1} + C_{m2} + C_{m3} + \dots + C_{mn}$$

Were,

C= Total cost of marketing

C_f= Cost borne by the producer farmer from the time at which the produce leaves the farm till the scale of the produce.

C_m= cost incurred by the middleman in the process of buying and selling.

Marketing margin :-

A marketing margin is similar to a profit margin in that it shows the relationship between the amount a company pays for products and the amounts its customer pay.

a) Absolute margin- $P^{Ri} - (P_{pi} + C_{mi})$

b) Percent margin $\frac{P^{Ri} - (P_{pi} + C_{mi})}{P^{Ri}} \times 100$

Marketing Efficiency:

Marketing efficiency is the degree of the market performance. It is the ratio of market output to market input.

$$\text{Market efficiency} = \frac{\text{Output}}{\text{Input}}$$

$$\text{Percentage} = (100(R_{ij} - 0.5))/N_j$$

s.no	Particulars (unit 10 kg)	Channel 1	Channel 2	Channel 3	Channel 4
1.	Net price received by producer	3500	3500	3500	3500
2.	Marketing cost incurred by producer	-	24	24	24
3.	Price paid by trader	-		3674	3674
4.	Expenses incurred by trader	-		90.5	90.5
5.	Margin of trader	-		80	80
6.	Price paid by wholesaler	-	3681	4150	4150
7.	Expenses incurred by wholesaler	-	170	217	217
8.	Margin of wholesaler	-	50	100	120
9.	Price paid by processor		-	-	470
10.	Consumer price	3681	4025.5	4356.5	6235
11.	Total marketing margin	-	50	240.5	680
12.	Total marketing cost	180.5	335.5	786.5	1259
13.	Price spread	180.5	335.5	786.5	1259
14.	Total marketing efficiency	20.39	11.99	5.53	4.95

Table1:- The above table show that total marketing cost shared by producer of different channel are Rs-180.5, Rs-335.5, Rs-786.5/-Rs-1259/-, marketing margin indulge Rs-50, Rs-240, Rs-680/- and marketing efficiency shared by producer is 20.39, 11.39, 5.53, 4.95 by the producer.

Constraints in makhana production

Constraints faced by the farmer in makhana production and marketing are defined in below chart-

S.no	Particulars	Garret score	Garret rank
1.	Price fluctuation	88	VI
2.	Lack of government scheme	79	II
3.	Unorganised market	74	IV
4.	Lack of storage facility	70	VII
5.	Lack of skilled labour	66	V
6.	High commission charges	64	X
7.	Lack of credit facility	61	IX
8.	Lack of availability of market information	58	III
9.	Commission agent	56	VIII
10.	Lack of transport facility	52	I

Suggestion

Expansion of area under makhana.

Adoption of high yielding variety.

Mechanization for harvesting and processing.

Allocation of separate HS code.

Conclusion

The present investigation was aimed for analyzing the marketing cost, marketing margin, marketing efficiency, price spread of makhana in Darbhanga District of Bihar (India). In the study area the farmer were the first actor in makhana marketing, but they did not get the fair price. They have limited scope of value addition. The main objective is to study on marketing cost, marketing margin, marketing efficiency, Garrett's ranking Technique. Producer share in consumer rupee and price spread. The priority attention by the government

should be given to the farmers so that they can contribute largely to the growth of farmer.

References

1. **Chaitanya A. GI 211** portfolio analysis for enhancing income of makhana growers in Bihar, project report PGDM, NAARM,
2. **Jain A, Singh HB, Kinjal PB2010.** economics of Fox nut cultivation. A case study from Manipur in North eastern India. Indian journal for natural product and resource
3. **Jha S N, Parshad S. 1996** .gorgon fruit or makhana- Its cultivation and processing. Indian horticulture; 39(2): 18-20.